

Terpenoids. Part XCVII : Synthesis of Methylether of Elvirol

O. P. VIG, A. K. VIG, I. J. PURI and V. D. AHUJA

Department of Chemistry, Panjab University, Chandigarh

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2-Methoxy-5-methylacetophenone(III) on condensation with ethyl cyano-acetate gives acrylate (IV). The compound (IV) on hydrogenation with Pd/C followed by hydrolysis affords acid (VI). Esterification of (VI) and subsequent reduction provides carbinol (VIII) which on reaction with PBr_3 gives bromide (IX). Treatment of (IX) with NaCN furnishes nitrile (X) which on alcoholysis with HCl-EtOH affords ester (XI). Reduction of (XI) and subsequent oxidation with Collins' reagent provides aldehyde (XIII). Wittig reaction with isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane on aldehyde (XIII) yields the methyl ether of elvirol (II).

THE sesquiterpenic phenol, elvirol, was isolated by Bohlmann and Grenz¹ from *Elvira biflora* DC. Structure (I) was assigned to this compound on the basis of spectral studies. Recently they have also achieved the synthesis² and placed its constitution on firm footing. In the present communication, we report a synthesis of the methyl ether of elvirol(II) using Wittig reaction for the fixation of isopropylidene grouping.

Cope-Knoevenagel condensation of 2-methoxy-5-methylacetophenone (III) with ethylcyanoacetate³

afforded the acrylate (IV). The ester (IV) was reduced catalytically in almost quantitative yield with Pd/C to ethyl 2-cyano-3-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propanoate (V) which on hydrolysis with Conc. HCl gave acid (VI). Esterification of (VI) provided ester (VII) which was subsequently reduced with LAH to the corresponding alcohol (VIII). On treatment with PBr_3 , the carbinol (VIII) furnished bromide (IX) which was converted into nitrile (X) with NaCN using DMSO as solvent⁴. The cyanide (X) on alcoholysis⁵ with ethanol saturated with hydrogen chloride gas, gave ester (XI). LAH reduction of ester (XI) in dry ether, followed by oxidation with modified Collins' reagent⁶ produced the aldehyde (XIII). Finally, the chromatographically pure aldehyde was subjected to Wittig reaction with isopropylidetriphenylphosphorane to yield the methyl ether of elvirol (II). The synthetic product was purified by column chromatography. The identity of the synthetic compound (II) was confirmed through its IR and NMR spectra.

Experimental

Boiling points are uncorrected. IR spectra (thin films) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer infracord spectrophotometer with NaCl optics. NMR spectrum was recorded using CCl_4 as solvent and TMS as internal standard at 60 MHz.

Ethyl 2-cyano-3-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-acrylate (IV) :

A mixture of ketone (III, 85 g) ethyl cyanoacetate (113 g), ammonium acetate (15.5 g), acetic acid (48 g) and dry benzene (300 ml) was refluxed using Dean and Stark apparatus for 15 hr. The contents were added to water and the organic substance extracted in ether-benzene. Vacuum distillation of the product gave (IV, 50 g), in 61% yield, b.p., 190°-200°/5 mm; γ_{max} 2215 cm^{-1} (-CN), 1700 cm^{-1} (unsaturated ester). (Found : N, 5.32. $C_{15}H_{17}O_3N$ requires N, 5.40%).

Ethyl 2-cyano-3-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propionate (V) :

The alkylidene ester (IV, 40 g) was reduced in alcohol (98%, 200 ml) and acetic acid (3 ml) with Pd/C (5%, 5 g). Hydrogen (5400 ml) was absorbed yielding the reduction product (35 g, 90%), bp. 190°-200°/6 mm; γ_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} (saturated ester carbonyl). (Found: N, 5.26. $C_{15}H_{19}O_3N$ requires N, 5.36%).

3-Methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propionic acid (VI) :

The cyanoester (V, 130 g) was refluxed with conc. HCl (750 ml) for about 50 hr. After cooling the crude material (100 g, 80%) was obtained which was purified through its sodium salt (m.p. 90°-91°). IR showed no peak at 2210 cm^{-1} (-CN). (Found: C, 69.14; H, 7.84. $C_{12}H_{16}O_3$ requires C, 69.21; H, 7.74%).

Ethyl 3-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propionate (VII) :

The mixture of acid (VI, 35 g), alcohol (40 ml), benzene (120 ml) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1.5 ml) was heated for 8 hr using a constant water separator. After decomposition with $NaHCO_3$ solution, the organic phase was dried. Removal of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation afforded the ester (VII, 25 g) in 72% yield b.p. 165°-70°/7 mm, γ_{max} 1725 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl). (Found: C, 68.01; H, 9.64. $C_{14}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 67.89; H, 9.50%).

3-Methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propanol (VIII) :

Ester (VII, 11.5 g) was reduced with LAH (2.2 g) in ether (150 ml). After decomposing with a saturated solution of sodium potassium tartrate, the aqueous was extracted with ether and dried. Removal of the solvent and subsequent distillation afforded the alcohol (VIII, 7 g) in 61% yield, b.p. 160°/62°/8 mm; γ_{max} 3350, 1030 cm^{-1} (-OH). (Found: C, 74.02; H, 9.42. $C_{12}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 74.19; H, 9.34%).

3-Methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl) propylbromide (IX) :

Alcohol (VIII, 20 g) was treated with PBr_3 (10.2 g) using ether (200 ml) as a solvent containing a few drops of pyridine. After decomposing with $NaHCO_3$ solution, the solvent was removed and it (IX) was used as such for the next operation without further purification

1-Cyano-3-methyl-3-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)propane (X) :

The bromide (IX, 21 g) was added in 10 min to a warm (60°) stirred mixture of NaCN (4.4 g) in DMSO (20 ml). The temp. was maintained 55°-60° during addition and the contents were further heated for 2 hr at 60°. The contents were poured into iced water and the organic layer was extracted with

ether. Evaporation of the solvent followed by vacuum distillation provided nitrile (X, 14 g) in 80% yield. The IR showed the appearance of a band at 2215 cm^{-1} ($C \equiv N$). (Found: N, 6.74. $C_{13}H_{17}ON$ requires N, 6.89%).

Ethyl 4-methyl-4-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)butanoate (XI) :

A slow stream of HCl was bubbled into a mixture of nitrile (X, 20.3 g) in ethanol (20.7 g). The resulting heat of the solution made the solvent to reflux. After 30 min, the reaction mixture was treated with water (4 ml), warmed on steam bath for 20 min and poured into an excess of ice cold water. The solution was extracted with ether. The ethereal extract washed with water, sodium bicarbonate solution and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue was distilled under vacuum to furnish the ester (XI) in 70% yield, b.p. 152°-55°/7 mm; γ_{max} 1735 cm^{-1} (ester carbonyl) (Found: C, 71.84; H, 8.91. $C_{15}H_{20}O_3$ requires C, 71.97; H, 8.85%).

4-Methyl 4-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-butanol (XII) :

The ester (XI, 11 g) was reduced with LAH (1.85 g) in ether as given under VIII to produce alcohol (XII, 7.4 g). The IR showed absence of peaks in the carbonyl region but showed characteristic bands in the hydroxyl region. (Found: C, 74.84; H, 9.63. $C_{13}H_{20}O_2$ requires C, 74.96; H, 9.68%).

4-Methyl 4-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-butanol (XIII) :

Chromium trioxide (12 g) was added to a stirred solution of pyridine (19 ml) and dry methylene chloride (30 ml). The yellow coloured complex thus formed was stirred for 20 min at room temp. To this was added the alcohol (XII, 4 g) in (5 ml) of dry methylene chloride. A tarry black deposit separated immediately and this was further stirred for 30 min. There after it was poured into ice cold water and extracted with methylene chloride. The combined organic phase was dried ($CaCl_2$). The solvent was distilled off and the residue was chromatographed over alumina using pet. ether as eluent. The product so obtained was distilled under reduced pressure to obtain the aldehyde (XIII, 2.5 g) in 62% yield. γ_{max} 2700, 1710 cm^{-1} (-CHO). (Found: C, 75.58; H, 8.92. $C_{13}H_{18}O_2$ requires C, 75.69; H, 8.80%).

2,6-Dimethyl-6-(2'-methoxy-5'-methylphenyl)-2-hexene (II) :

Isopropylidene triphenylphosphorane was prepared from NaH (0.68 g), DMSO (7 ml) and isopropyl triphenylphosphonium iodide (6.04 g) in DMSO (14 ml). To this was added the aldehyde (XIII, 2 g) in dry THF (3 ml) with continuous stirring. The reaction mixture was kept overnight at room temp. and then poured into ice cold water. The organic layer was extracted with pet. ether, washed with water and dried. The solvent was removed and the residue was purified by chromatography over neutral alumina and subsequent distillation under diminished pressure

to furnish (I, 1.5 g) in 80% yield, b.p. 115°–120°/6 mm; γ_{max} 2950, 1470, 1435, 1360, 1320, 1295, 1250, 1180, 1160, 1155, 1100, 1040, 995, 960, 880, 805, 740 and 690 cm^{-1} . NMR exhibited signals at τ : 2.91 (1 H, s, Ar-H), 3.08–3.32 (1 H each, d, Ar-H), 4.68 (1 H, m, olefinic), 6.05 (3 H, $-\text{OCH}_3$), 7.51 (1 H, q, methine), 7.76 (3 H, s, Ar-Me), 8.1 (2 H, m, allylic methylene), 8.42 (8 H, m, allylic methyl and methylene protons) and 8.84 (3 H, d, H-C-Me). (Found : C, 82.64; H, 10.38. $\text{C}_{16}\text{H}_{24}\text{O}$ requires C, 82.70; H, 10.42%).

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